

INTERPERSONAL COMPETENCIES AMONG PUBLIC SCHOOL HEADS: ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the relationship between interpersonal competencies and job performance of the school heads in Lapu-Lapu City Division for the school year 2023- 2024 as the basis for a proposed enhancement program. A Descriptive -correlational design was used since the researcher looked on the relationship between the level of interpersonal competencies and the level of job performance of the school heads. The results revealed that the level of interpersonal competencies of the school heads and master teachers were Very Satisfactory in role management, learning and training, understanding and motivating, positive attitudes and problem-solving techniques. On the level of job performance of the school heads based on Office Performance Commitment Review Form in terms of instructional leadership, learning environment, human resource management and development, school leadership and management operation and parents' involvement and community partnership and plus factor were Outstanding. The results further revealed a significant relationship between interpersonal competencies and job performance, likewise showed significant relationship between understanding and motivating and school leadership and management operation. The researcher concluded that the relationship between interpersonal competencies and job performance of school heads in Lapu-Lapu City Division underscores the importance of these skills in educational leadership. Effective interpersonal competencies enable school heads to lead more efficiently, foster a positive work environment, engage with the community, and support student success. Enhancing these competencies through professional development and training can lead to improved job performance and more successful school management.

Keywords: Interpersonal Competencies, Job Performance, School Heads, Descriptive-Correlational Design, Lapu-Lapu City Division

INTRODUCTION

Everyone has a chance to become a leader, but only few are considered to be called great leaders. A great leader is the one who is able to inspire others and be a role model in a team or in an organization. Leadership is the art of motivating a group of people to act toward achieving a common goal to have a better result for the betterment of everyone. The roles and functions of a leader in an entity is very vital. The goals and objectives established by the organization are perpetually achieved without someone assuming complete responsibility; therefore, to be effective leaders, school heads need to take into account their interpersonal skills (Tampan, 2021). School heads have faced difficulties and challenges in achieving educational goals. These involve their interpersonal skills and job performance where in school heads have foster ineffective communication, lack of feedback, they did not demonstrate social awareness among teachers, and some school heads did not encourage empathy. Some school heads did not have a strong conflict resolution with their teachers.

Interpersonal competence pertains to the ability and capability of the school heads being a leader of the school to select what best communication that is most effective in a given situation. Such competency empowers individuals to achieve the goals of any exchange of ideas in a manner that is best suited for all involved in the conversation. In addition, interpersonal competencies of a school head can be manifested by his ability to deal and interact with the people and the community. This competency also includes the ability to maintain good relationships which are beneficial for collaboration and for the development in the workplace. Interpersonal competencies are directed at different people and shows human relations to anything occurring between individuals such as interpersonal communication. And on the other this competency of a person talks about anything inward relating to the inner life and thoughts of oneself.

In the Netherlands, schools' heads as the chief executive of the school system have displayed constant values in dealing with their teachers, parents, students and workmates and considered the cultural diversity of the people. However, this cannot be generalized because people have differences in the composition and interpersonal competence (Velman, 2019). Based on the results from the study of Saraswati (2018), it was found out that interpersonal competencies were shown through interactions with their peers who were from different cultures. He observed that to improve their interpersonal competence the school leaders should learn on how to carry struggles and conflict.

In Lapu-Lapu City Division, interpersonal competence is among the essential requirements of the school leaders and teachers to relate learning through interactions. In the new normal set up of learning, strong interpersonal competencies are required. Training and attending seminars on interpersonal competence to support teaching, learning, instructions and leadership platforms will be available for school leaders, teachers, parents and students. Lapu-Lapu City Division strongly supports DepEd's program and activities on providing quality relevant and accessible education in the new normal way of teaching and learning. The division responds to the need for improving interpersonal competence for better education, initiate activities that boast school heads' competence for the learning process.

The researcher observed in the local scenario in her 3 years of teaching experiences, there are issues and concerns that contribute to measuring interpersonal competencies and job performance among school heads. This issue includes the attitudes of teachers, students and parents, family concerns, and monetary resource to achieve projects and programs of the school. One of the significant factors to have progressive school environment is the quality and performance of the school leaders in the educational system. They have varied functions, as stated in the Education Act of 1982. They are accountable for the efficient and effective administration and management of the school. They must develop and maintain a healthy school atmosphere conducive to promoting and preserving academic freedom. They are also eyeing effective teaching and learning, for harmonious and progressive school-personal relationships. Moreover, they assume and maintain professional behavior in his/ her work and deal with students, teachers, parents, stakeholders, administrative staff, and others.

Panol, et al (2020) mentioned that all of this aim to address the 21st century's educational needs. A school head helps the school to attain a high level of performance through the utilization of its resources. It is expected that the school head as leader and manager has the knowledge, skills, and ability to promote the success of the students by managing the school organization, operation, and resources in a way that promotes a safe, efficient and effective learning environment.

Another instance is weak leadership and managerial skills of school heads regarding financial planning and organizing school programs and projects (Ruyhen, 2021). This was supported by Lillejord (2019), that the lack of professionalism and managerial skills and not dedicated to the system is also a problem in the area of accountability and management in an organization was poor job performance.

Therefore, there is an immediate need to enhance the interpersonal competences of the school heads as leaders and teachers to have better learning outcomes. For a school leader to be effective, she or she has to be a good example and should have strong decision making to any undertaking in the school. They should upgrade their interpersonal competence and leadership skills to perform better in school dynamics. These interpersonal competencies that need to be considered are role management, learning and training, understanding and motivating, positive attitudes; and problem -solving techniques. As stipulated in the Code of Professional Ethic for Public School Teachers, effective school leaders demand responsible leadership in instruction and performance. School heads should at all times show professional courtesy, sympathy, and good interactions with the people surrounded with strong interpersonal competences.

A school leader should therefore, be idealistic and yet practical in his or her relationship with the subordinates in an organization. Understanding of people's differences makes the relationship smoother. This can influence them to think, feel, and interact accordingly. This was supported by Mann (2021) that human relations include the ability to understand and accept feelings, attitudes and motives of others for what they say and perform should establish effective relations.

Therefore, a school leader should maintain a good relationship with his/her people because all aspects affecting the organization, if not resolved properly, will result in disaster and poor performance as a whole. A school leader shows actions and always stands for what is best for the school's effectiveness. A school leader must be a good speaker and wise listener and observe with high respect the opinions of others.

Therefore, the researcher would like to determine if interpersonal competencies really have an impact on the job performance of the school heads. And by then the result of this will be the basis of creating enhancement program.

Theoretical Background

This study is anchored on Interpersonal Communication Competence Theory by Spitzberg & Cupach, (1984). This theory explains the ability to choose a communication behavior that is both appropriate and effective for a given situation. Interpersonal competence allows one to achieve their communication goals without causing the other party to lose face. This has three components namely; knowledge, skill, and motivation. Knowledge simply means knowing what behavior is best suited for a given situation. Skill is having the ability to apply that behavior in the given context. Motivation is having the desire to communicate in a competent manner.

This is also supported in Behavioral Leadership Theory by Rensis Likert (1950) as cited in Hall (2019). The behavioral theory is not just a theory on a leader or school administrator's behavior, but this focuses on how the leaders performed his role with high value. The school administrators showed the traits in which can be emulated by other leaders in sustaining the smooth sailing of the organization as a whole. This theory further suggests that administrators and leaders are not born successful, but these behaviors can be created and acquired based on learnable behavior from other people and the environment. Behavioral leadership theory argues that a leader's success is based on their behavior rather than their natural attributes. Behavioral leadership theory involves observing and evaluating a leader's actions and behaviors when they are responding to a specific situation. Thus, primarily focuses more on the actions and thoughts of a great leader. The actions of leaders can be best predictor for the success of organization. He has to put his words into actions that is worth emulating. The actions rather than qualities are the focal points of behavioral learning theory. Good behavior is viewed and categorized as "styles of leadership" in this theory. Some of the leadership styles of a leader, manager, and administrator include functional leader, people-oriented leader, task-oriented leader, and total responsibility person. However, what matters most is the actions and behaviors of a leader, which totally defines accountability for success (Custodio, 2020).

Literature Review

Interpersonal Competence of Effective School Heads

Kambeya (2019) cited that in Georgia US, interpersonal competencies required face-to face communication as preferred by teachers in the teacher-principal dyad. Interpersonal competencies, behavior, attitudes, and ideas of the principals will be affected by the performance of teachers in managing school dynamics. He added that principals as chief executive of the school have always looked at the objectives, goals, missions and vision of the school. However, he found out that face-to-face interactions to the teachers were most difficult for principals to sustain. Poor interpersonal communication of the principal could be affected to the emotional states of teachers such as depression, low-self-esteem, feelings of incompetence, and seeking a new place of employment. When principals demonstrated good interpersonal communication skills, the teachers were motivated to give more than 100% effort. Teachers' perceptions of their principal were manifested in their efforts to do their jobs.

Role Management of the School Heads

According to Muhamad (2019), the interpersonal communication and skills of the school head in Indonesia contributes greatly and has positive effect on the performance of teachers. This means role management as coined to improving interpersonal competencies are the top priority in their educational system. The level of leadership training as the chief executive in the school and who is an educational leader is very decisive in the school management and governance thus the leadership role will be reflected in his role and task. This means that the performance of school heads is a determining factor for the quality of education that will implicate on quality of education output.

According to Parlak, (2021) that school leaders must have strong interpersonal competence. This can assure the role management which will be at the same time organizational managers and school leaders for transparency in accordance with the law and its regulations during the administration and leadership of organizational goals. This interpersonal competence also indicates a social relationship in which the administrator feels required to answer to higher authorities regarding the accuracy of their actions.

Tacsi and Koc (2021), found out that the role management of a school leader makes positive contributions to an organization or school institution in terms of attitudes such as school performance, trust in leaders, the need for independence, feedback regarding tasks, and satisfaction received from responsibilities. Polat (2018) agreed that these principles are also becoming more and more important in the identification and prevention of conflict within the organization.

Learning and Training Competence of School Heads

Mohrman (2019) stated that the performance of the school heads should be in school-based management which decentralizes control from the central district office to individual schools as a way to give school constituents -- principals, teachers, parents, and community members -- more control over what happens in schools. The SBM is adopted for the purpose of having school development and improvement. By empowering the performance of the school heads will be better tailored to address the needs of school such as students' need, teachers' need and the school performance as a whole. This can be achieved by strengthening the competence of the school leader through training and seminars.

Understanding and Motivating Competence of the School Heads

Soder (2019) cited that within the school system, subordinates are often evaluated by a superior to sustain the standards and expectations, which means that the competency and performance are located within hierarchical practices of bureaucracy. He pointed out that this is an important dimension of professionalism and ethics of school leaders. This dimension highlights that the leader is morally responsive to the teachers, students and the parents' needs, as well as responsive to the public through the mechanism of the school's effectiveness. In moral terms understanding and motivating can be seen by keeping to ethical standards held by school leaders as a group and as individuals.

Positive Attitudes Competence of the School Heads

Guillermo and De Guzman (2019) mentioned that a positive attitude is highly required where tensions, conflicts, contradictions and discontinuity continue to challenge the school management. At this level, the school heads need not just only be competent in the performance of their multitude of tasks, but above all, they are bound to show a certain degree of interpersonal reflectivity. This reflectivity calls for the school head to revisit, reconsider and re-evaluate the different inputs, processes and products in the school environment which are not only measurable but valuable as well.

Problem -Solving Techniques Competence of the School Heads

As cited by Wohlstetter (2019) that of the competencies of the school heads in actively restructuring School Based Management (SBM) at school level is problem solver. School leaders should help to appraise the school-wide teachers' growth and development to improve the performance in school. This in contrary to the idea of Albers (2018), he believed that if the school system could not afford to train all teachers, then possibly the school head look for ways either few of teachers were trained with the expectation and these teachers would have to share their new knowledge and skills with the whole teachers through Learning Action Cell. This is a manifestation that an effective school heads would always look to encourage faculty development for the best school effectiveness.

Instructional Leadership as Job Performance of the School Heads

According to Good and Brophy (2019) that one of the job performances of a school leader must strong instructional leadership including the teachers and learners on focusing a positive self-fulfilling prophecy effect. This shall create a warm social relationship with others, give them more feedback about their performance in the classroom. A school leader must share input and give them more opportunities to respond and ask questions or output. There will be a supervision of the school leaders with the teachers in providing necessary instructional help especially the beginning teachers.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This study is quantitative in approach utilizing descriptive -correlational research design in investigating the interpersonal competencies and performance of the school heads at Lapu-Lapu City Division. Descriptive correlational design is used when determining the nature of the relationship between variables without looking into the cause and is summarized using descriptive statistics. Correlational research designs measure two or more relevant variables and assess a relationship between or among them (Ojo, 2019).

Descriptive -correlational design since the researcher looked the relationship between the level of interpersonal competencies of the school heads in terms of role management, learning and training, understanding and motivating, positive attitudes, and problem -solving techniques to the level of job performance of the school heads based on OPCRf as manifested by their instructional leadership, learning environment, human resource management and development, school leadership and management operation; and parents' involvement and community partnership and plus factor.

This research study further aimed to gather information relevant to phenomenon using a documentary analysis of the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form (OPCRf) of the school heads that is existing and to identify the recent situation and practices for the future plans and actions. Document analysis is a method of collecting data because it relies on the compilation and analysis of existing organizational records, documentation and information. Documentary analysis is used in the study both a technique for collecting and analyzing data on the interpersonal competencies and job performance of the schools in Lapu-Lapu City Division. As a technique for data collection and analysis, it is used to complement other means of collecting and analyzing data, with a view to making the study object easier to understand.

Population of the Study

There were 46 school heads in which four were from districts 1, 5, 6, and 8, while three respondents in district 2 and 5. There were two respondents in districts 3 and six respondents in districts 4 and 9, there were five respondents in districts 7 and seven respondents in district 10. Moreover, there were 30 master teachers in which three were coming from each district with a grand total of 44 respondents. The respondents selected through the simple random sample technique are those chosen randomly from a clearly defined population, ensuring unbiased and representative data.

Data Gathering Tool

The study utilized research instruments adapted from the OPCR of the school heads to effectively gather relevant data in relation to the content of the study. Office Performance Review and Commitment Form (OPCRF) Evaluating the performance of the school heads to be rated by respondents to gather the necessary data. They described the duties and responsibilities of teachers across career stages; the Key Result Areas (KRAs) for the realization of those duties and the specific objectives to attain the KRAs. They also present in detail the various Means of Verification (MOV) that served as proof of the attainment of specific objectives alongside performance indicators, from outstanding to poor performance in the assessment process.

Methods

This study is quantitative in approach utilized descriptive -correlational research design in investigating the interpersonal competencies and performance of the school heads at Lapu-Lapu City Division. Descriptive correlational design is used when determining the nature of the relationship between variables without looking into the cause and is summarized using descriptive statistics. Correlational research designs measure two or more relevant variables and assess a relationship between or among them (Ojo, 2019). Descriptive -correlational design since the researcher looked the relationship between the level of interpersonal competencies of the school heads in terms of role management, learning and training, understanding and motivating, positive attitudes, and problem -solving techniques to the level of job performance of the school heads based on OPCR as manifested by their instructional leadership, learning environment, human resource management and development, school leadership and management operation; and parents' involvement and community partnership and plus factor.

Data Gathering Procedures

Pre Data Gathering. The gathering of data were done by asking permission from the Dean of the Graduate studies of University of the Visayas address (Appendix A) which will be attached to the letter request asking permission to conduct the study from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Department of Education, Lapu-Lapu City Division (Appendix B) to guarantee the support of the School Heads. It is important to realize that informed permission cannot be given from an organizational representative until you have received ethical approval from the university. Furthermore, the researcher will secure an informed consent from the respondents of the study. The goal of the informed consent process is to provide sufficient information to a potential participant, in a language which is easily understood by the participant, so that he/she can make the voluntary decision regarding "to" or "not to" participate in the research study. As soon as the researcher will be granted the permission or the notice to proceed from the institutional review board. The researcher starts to conduct the study on the date scheduled.

Actual Data Gathering. The researcher secured a transmittal letter address to the Schools Division Superintendent of Lapu-Lapu City Division (Appendix B) to guarantee the support of the school heads in each school. The researcher utilized any platform in sending the permission letter, it could be via Google form, Facebook or Messenger.

As soon as the permission is granted the study was implemented on the date scheduled. The survey questionnaire was administered to the respondents via Google forms, Facebook or Messenger to the Elementary School Heads of Lapu-Lapu City Division. If intervention is needed, then the researcher accommodated the queries via any of those platforms during the conduct of data gathering. The respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire. The accomplished tool was retrieved immediately after the respondents answered the questionnaires in the Google form.

Post Data Gathering. After the questionnaires has been answered by the school head this will be gathered, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools. After all, the raw data were placed in a secure cabinet and it was treated only after a year.

Data Analysis

The scores that were collected and collated will be treated using appropriate data analysis tools. Statistical parameters and formulas were used to measure and evaluate the scores of the respondents. To determine the demographic profile of the respondents' frequency count and percentage were used. To determine the level of interpersonal competencies and job performance of the respondents, mean and standard deviation were used. To

determine the significant relationship between demographic profile and the level of interpersonal competencies and job performance of the respondents, Person -r and Chi-Square statistical tool were used.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting this research, the researcher highly observed ethical consideration for the following reasons: The researcher is highly promoting the goals of academic research, such as expanding the knowledge. The researcher supports the values that are required for collaborative work, such as mutual respect and fairness. This is important because research results depend on collaborative efforts between the researcher and respondents. Thus, the researcher is accountable for their actions and highly observed the moral values and makes sure that everybody is not harmed.

Beneficence. The researcher has put in high consideration his obligation to support and protect the rights of the respondents in order to prevent harm and will put the respondents in any form of harm. Thus, the research will act kindness and utmost charity that will demonstrate benefits among the respondents.

Respect. Respect for Human Dignity Respect for human dignity is the second ethical principle in the Belmont Report. This principle includes the right to self-determination and the right to full disclosure. The research will always observe utmost respect and values each respondent's dignity to make sure that the respondents are given the free decision in the conduct of the study.

Justice. The third broad principle articulated in the Belmont Report concerns justice, which includes participants' right to fair treatment and their right to privacy. The researcher treats each of the respondents with fair, equal and just to avoid biases that will result conflict. This further aims to make sure that each respondent has shares equally and no one is exploited nor forced.

Protection of Human Rights

The researcher conducted the study on interpersonal competencies and performance of the school heads, however strict confidentiality of the study has observed during the data gathering of data from the respondents. The identity and salient parts of the data has been kept with utmost confidential. The rights to privacy plays a significant role in the research investigation and documentation which led to the development of right-based intervention.

Risk-Benefit Ratio Determination

The safety and security of the respondents is the utmost priority in this study, thus the researcher will make sure that no individual respondent will get in to harm. The researcher will not intimidate nor coerce any of the respondents as risk-benefit is concern. The research likewise respects to whatever are the responses of the respondents. And researcher make sure that there are no adverse effects on emotional, psychological and financial aspects of the respondents.

A. Content, Comprehension and Documentation of the Informed Consent

Participants Status. Prospective participants need to understand the distinction between research and treatment. They should be told which healthcare activities are routine and which are implemented specifically for the study. They also should be informed that data they provide will be used for research purposes.

Study Goals. The overall goals of the research should be stated, in lay rather than technical terms. The use to which the data will be put should be described.

Type of Data. Prospective participants should be told what type of data will be collected. Specify it is quantitative or qualitative.

Procedures. Prospective participants should be given a description of the data collection procedures and of procedures to be used in any innovative treatment.

Nature of Commitment. Participants should be told the expected time commitment at each point of contact and the number of contacts within a given time frame.

Sponsorship. Information on who is sponsoring or funding the study should be noted; if the research is part of an academic requirement, this information should be shared.

Participant's Selection. Prospective participants should be told how they were selected for recruitment and how many people will be participating.

Risk. Physical harm, including unanticipated side effects • Physical discomfort, fatigue, or boredom • Psychological or emotional distress resulting from self-disclosure, introspection, fear of the unknown, discomfort with strangers, fear of eventual repercussions, anger or embarrassment at the type of questions being asked • Social risks, such as the risk of stigma, adverse effects on personal relationships, loss of status • Loss of privacy • Loss of time • Monetary costs (e.g., for transportation, child care, time lost from work)

Potential Risk. Prospective participants should be informed of any foreseeable risks (physical, psychological, social, or economic) or discomforts and efforts that will be taken to minimize risks. The possibility of unforeseeable risks should also be discussed, if appropriate. If injury or damage is possible, treatments that will be made available to participants should be described. When risks are more than minimal prospective participants should be encouraged to seek advice before consenting.

Benefits. Access to a potentially beneficial intervention that might otherwise be unavailable to them • Comfort in being able to discuss their situation or problem with a friendly, objective person • Increased knowledge about themselves or their conditions, either through opportunity for introspection and self-reflection or through direct interaction with researchers • Escape from normal routine, excitement of being part of a study • Satisfaction that information they provide may help others with similar problems or conditions • Direct monetary or material gains through stipends or other incentives.

Potential Benefits. Other possible benefits is highly considered in the study for both the researcher and the respondents.

Alternatives. If appropriate, participants should be told about alternative procedures or treatments that might be advantageous to them.

Incentives and Compensation. If stipends or reimbursements are to be paid (or if treatments are offered without fee), these arrangements should be discussed. Declare if its monetary or not and if it's not what are your other options in giving back to the respondents

Confidentiality Pledge. Prospective participants should be assured that their privacy will at all times be protected. If anonymity can be guaranteed, this should be stated.

Confidentiality Procedures. • Study participants have the right to expect that data they provide will be kept in strict confidence. Participants' right to privacy is protected through various confidentiality procedures. Anonymity, the most secure means of protecting confidentiality, occurs when the researcher cannot link participants to their data. • When anonymity is impossible, confidentiality procedures need to be implemented. A promise of confidentiality is a pledge that any information participants provide will not be publicly reported in a manner that identifies them, and will not be accessible to others. This means that research information should not be shared with strangers nor with people known to participants (e.g., relatives, others), unless participants give explicit permission to do so. Researchers can take a number of steps to ensure that a breach of confidentiality does not occur, including the following: • Obtain identifying information (e.g., name, address) from participants only when essential. • Assign an identification (ID) number to each participant and attach the ID number rather than other identifiers to the actual data. • Maintain identifying information in a locked file. • Restrict access to identifying information to only a few people on a need-to-know basis. • Enter no identifying information onto computer files. • Destroy identifying information as quickly as practical. • Make research personnel sign confidentiality pledges if they have access to data or identifying information. • Report research information in the aggregate; if information for an individual is reported, disguise the person's identity, such as through the use of a fictitious name.

Authorization to Access Private Information. • Discuss whether obtained separately or as part of the consent form. • Include who will receive the information.

Voluntary Consent. Researchers should indicate that participation is strictly voluntary and that failure to volunteer will not result in any penalty or loss of benefits.

Right to Withdraw and withhold Information. Prospective participants should be told that, after consenting, they have the right to withdraw from the study or to withhold any specific piece of information. Researchers may need to describe circumstances under which researchers would terminate the study.

Contact Information. The researcher should tell participants whom they could contact in the event of further questions, comments, or complaints. UV-IRB Ethics Review Panel (specify) has approved the study, and may be reached through the following contact information regarding rights of study participants, including grievances and complaints:

2nd Floor, Administration Building
Colon Street, Cebu City
Telephone No. (032) 416-8607 or email at: uvirb2015@gmail.com

B. Debriefing, Communications and Referrals

Researchers can often show their respect for participants—and proactively minimize emotional risks—by carefully attending to the nature of the interactions they have with them. For example, researchers should always be gracious and polite, should phrase questions tactfully, and should be sensitive to cultural and linguistic diversity. Researchers can also use more formal strategies to communicate respect and concern for participants' well-being. For example, it is sometimes useful to offer debriefing sessions after data collection is completed to permit participants to ask questions or air complaints.

Debriefing is especially important when the data collection has been stressful or when ethical guidelines had to be "bent" (e.g., if any deception was used in explaining the study).

It is also thoughtful to communicate with participants after the study is completed to let them know that their participation was appreciated. Finally, in some situations, researchers may need to assist study participants by making referrals to appropriate health, social, or psychological services

C. Conflict of Interest

Discuss the conflict of interest and ask the statement of agreement to IRB for the template. A conflict of interest is a situation in which financial or other personal considerations have the potential to compromise or bias professional judgment and objectivity. An apparent conflict of interest is one in which a reasonable person would think that the professional's judgment is likely to be compromised. A potential conflict of interest involves a situation that may develop into an actual conflict of interest. It is important to note that a conflict of interest exists whether or not decisions are affected by a personal interest; a conflict of interest implies only the potential for bias, not likelihood. It is also important to note that a conflict of interest is not considered misconduct in research, since the definition for misconduct is currently limited to fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism.

D. Treatment of Vulnerability Groups (Provide discussion in this section if it is applicable in your study)

Vulnerable populations may be incapable of giving fully informed consent (e.g., mentally retarded people) or may be at risk of unintended side effects because of their circumstances (e.g., pregnant women). Researchers interested in studying high-risk groups should understand guidelines governing informed consent, risk/benefit assessments, and acceptable research procedures for such groups. In general, research with vulnerable groups should be undertaken only when the risk/benefit ratio is low or when there is no alternative (e.g., studies of childhood development require child participants).

Children. Legally and ethically, children do not have competence to give informed consent, so the informed consent of children's parents or legal guardians must be obtained. It is appropriate, however—especially if the child is at least 7 years old—to obtain the child's assent as well. Assent refers to the child's affirmative agreement to participate. If the child is mature enough (e.g., a 12-year-old) to understand basic informed consent information, it is advisable to obtain written assent from the child as well, as evidence of respect for the child's right to self-determination. Lindeke and colleagues (2000) and Kanner and colleagues (2004) provided guidance on children's assent and consent to participate in research. The U.S. government has issued special regulations (Subpart D of the Code of Federal Regulations, 2005) for the additional protection of children as study participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presented the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their educational attainment, seminars attended and year of leadership.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents (N=76)

Profile	f	%
Educational Attainment		
Doctoral Degree	13	17.11
Doctorate Acad. Reqt.	4	5.26
MA degree, Doctorate Acad. Reqt.	3	3.95

MA degree	17	22.37
MA Acad. Req't	29	38.16
BS Degree, MA degree, Doctorate Acad. Req't.	1	1.32
BS Degree, MA Acad. Req't	3	3.95
MA degree	17	22.37
Total	76	100
Seminars Attended		
International , National, Regional & Division	3	3.95
International , Regional & Division	2	2.63
International , Division	1	1.32
International	5	6.58
National, Regional & Division	5	6.58
National, Regional	1	1.32
National, Division	1	1.32
National	13	17.11
Regional & Division	10	13.16
Regional	12	15.79
Division	20	26.32
None	3	3.95
Total	76	100
Years of Leadership Experience		
21 and above	5	15.00
10 - 20 years	14	28.00
10 and below	57	57.00
Total	76	100

As reflected in the table above, it was found out that 29 out of 76 or 38.16% were MA Academic Requirement, 17 out of 76 or 22.37 % were MA degree, 13 out of 76 or 17.11% were having their Doctorate Degree, 6 out of 76 or 7.89% were BS Degree, 4 out of 76 or 5.26% were Doctorate Academic Requirement, 3 out of 76 or 3.95% were finished their BS Degree, MA Degree and have Doctorate Academic Requirement and only 1 out of 76 or 1.32% was BS Degree, MA degree, Doctorate Acad. Req't. This implies that majority of the School Heads and Master teachers had Master of Art completed the academic requirement. This means that earning a master's degree has advantages that many school heads and master teachers must look forward to. A school leader with a master's degree in education aligned to their competencies has provided greater opportunity since one of the requirements that a school leader and master teacher must be promoted is through earning higher professional degree. Through continuing education, it allows teachers to develop their specialized expertise in their area of interest.

This was supported by Llego (2021) that the reasons why school leaders such as school heads and master teachers pursue MA Academic Requirements is to avoid stagnate in their leadership and teaching career. The MA Academic Requirement swings open doors for school heads and master teachers of all educational opportunities. This will also help improve their leadership role and teaching pedagogy and practice. In the same vein Hammond and Snowden (2021) mentioned that school leaders and master teachers had gained priceless experience from earning a master's degree in education that they can use in improving teaching skills and competencies in education.

As reflected in the Table as to the training attended, there were 20 or 26.32% attended Division Level, 13 or 17.11 attended National Level, 12 attended Regional Level, 10 has attended both Regional and Division Level, 5 or 6.68 attended only International training, while another 5 where attended National, Regional and Division, 3 International , National, Regional & Division, 2 attended International , Regional & Division, 1 attended both International and Division Level, another 1 attended National & Division and another 1 attended both National & Regional and there were 3 not attended in any levels of training.

This means that teachers in the Department of Education should be necessary to attend training and seminars. Inspiring them to become better school leaders and master teachers in the modern world. Seminars will help create an effective leadership role for better learning environment, enhance teaching-learning scenarios, and keep them up to date on contemporary instructional devices. Leadership training is important for both experienced and those school leaders and master teachers who are new to the leadership profession to achieve the goal of the Department of Education on quality and functional in assessing teaching and learning.

The Department of Education in the country has strengthen on the professional growth of the school heads and master teachers by conducting varied training and seminars. The categorized the reasons of mid-year and year end training to following (Morgan, 2020). 1. it sharpen the skills of the school heads and master teachers, 2. it allows the school leaders and master teachers to learn new skills and strategies, 3. it increases their competencies and productivity, 4. it increases work qualities and 5. it helps school heads to be promoted their position.

As mentioned in DepEd Tambayan (2022) on DepEd issues new promotion policy, the training and seminars are very important in a teacher's life. The more training and seminars you attended, the more you gain knowledge. In addition to prior knowledge are also the certificates that come right after every training/seminar; therefore, you have to make sure to secure these pieces of papers as this will be your passport for promotion.

As supported by Morgan (2020) attending training and seminars would provide the school heads and master teachers with the chance to continue their professional development and pick up new techniques, approaches, tactics, abilities, and tools. School heads and master teachers who upgrade their skills immediately experience an increase in self-assurance, happiness, and motivation to work harder with their co teachers and students.

As reflected in the table above in years of leadership experience, it was found out that there were 57 out of 76 or 57% had leadership experience 10 years and below, 14 out of 76 of 14% had 10 - 20 years of experience and 5 out of 76 or 5% were 21 and above years of leadership experience. This implies that majority of the respondents had leadership experiences 10 years and below. This means that leadership experience matters but is not always a predictor of better performance of the school heads and master teachers. However, the impact of experience is strongest during the first few years of leadership role but does make assurance to be a predictor of their interpersonal competence. Therefore, it appears that less experienced school heads and master teachers were found to be given more attention compared to relatively more experienced considering that school heads and master teachers with more school teaching experience may not need training or support to function as part of their duties, accountability and responsibilities in school learning environment but the reality was not.

Harris and Tim (2019) support that throughout a school leader and master teacher's career, leadership experience is positively correlated with increases in overall school achievement. As school leaders master teachers gain experience, their students are more likely to do better and improve school performance. However, American Educational Research Association (2021) pointed out that the effectiveness of the school heads does not be measured of their years of experiences, but it depends on how passionate the school heads and master teachers are in their work.

Interpersonal Competence

Table 2 presented the interpersonal competence of the school heads and master teachers in Lapu-Lapu City Division in terms of role management.

Table 2. Interpersonal Competence of the Respondents in terms of Role Management

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Role Management			
1. Adjust and gets along faster with other teachers	4.355	0.626	Outstanding
2. Performs all jobs in his/her department	4.276	0.602	Outstanding
3. Cannot delegate one's final responsibility to anyone	2.908	1.338	Outstanding
4. Can handle a lot of details	4.211	0.660	Outstanding
5. Does not accept and carry out all orders from a representative of any department or school	2.382	1.326	Unsatisfactory
6. Has the technical know how	4.092	0.615	Very Satisfactory
7. Is open to subordinates	4.434	0.680	Outstanding
8. Is closer to his/her teachers than to the management	3.605	0.784	Very Satisfactory
9. Represents his/her teachers to top management	4.158	0.767	Very Satisfactory
10. Delegates responsibility and not authority	3.974	0.879	Very Satisfactory
Factor mean	3.840		Very Satisfactory

As shown in the Table 2 on interpersonal competencies of the school heads and master teachers in terms of role management and it was found out that the composite factor mean was 3.840 which interpreted as **Very Satisfactory**. An indicator rated as "unsatisfactory" for "Does not accept and carry out all orders from a representative of any department or school" suggests several important implications such as the teachers might show hesitancy or resistance in following orders from school officials or other sectors, suggesting possible problems with power dynamics. When this is labeled as "**unsatisfactory**" indicates that the school leaders are not adhering to

or executing the directives provided to them, potentially due to opposition, insufficient collaboration, or poor communication. This means that unsatisfactory level in this context would suggest that the school leaders are failing to fulfill the expectation of being attentive and collaborative in executing the directives and duties given to them.

This implies that the school heads and master teachers had establish and sustain an environment that fosters good relation as to their subordinates. Strong interpersonal skills in school leaders demonstrate effective communication and relationship-building abilities that are essential for creating a positive school atmosphere. Effective communication abilities encourage teamwork and shared responsibility among employees, fostering collaboration to achieve educational objectives. The school principals did not have full observation with the teachers on how the teachers performed their task in the delivery of learning applying the competencies. Effective role management of school heads and master teachers is crucial for fostering a positive school environment and improving overall educational outcomes. According to Stewart (2021) that the role of principal is helping teacher's professional development by sharing their expertise and experiences. There must be prompt feedback with the teachers to reevaluate their teaching methods in connections with the role management. This was supported by Marzano, Pickering, & Pollock (2019) cited that the principal's main focus should be to develop and maintain effective educational programs within his/her school and to promote the improvement of teaching and learning. As a school principal and instructional leader of the school, they must be equipped with duties and responsibilities in all school activities. For the delivery of high-quality educational initiatives, activities, and services, the school principals must assemble a team of support for the master teachers with the beginning teachers.

Table 3 presents the interpersonal competence of the school heads and master teachers in Lapu-Lapu City Division in terms of learning and training.

Table 3. Interpersonal Competence of the Respondents in terms of Learning and Training

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Learning and Training			
1. Is qualified to train other teachers	4.447	0.598	Very Satisfactory
2. Believes teaching is a complete only when the learner has learned	4.197	0.833	Very Satisfactory
3. Trains the teachers though busy in running the school/department	4.092	0.769	Very Satisfactory
4. Corrects the other teachers in front of others	1.947	1.142	Unsatisfactory
5. Shows in detail how the job is performed	4.211	0.680	Outstanding
6. Believes that a good instruction rule is to emphasize how not to do the job	2.461	1.280	Unsatisfactory
7. Checks that training is done in all departments	4.263	0.661	Outstanding
8. Agrees that a teacher of average intelligence should be able to do a job after he/she is told and shown how	3.763	0.978	Very Satisfactory
9. Agrees that learning curves and plateaus are important	4.145	0.743	Very Satisfactory
10. Does follow-ups to see how a teacher is doing	4.421	0.678	Outstanding
Factor mean	3.795		Very Satisfactory

As reflected in the Table 3 on interpersonal competencies of the school heads and master teachers in terms of learning and training. It was revealed that the composite factor mean was 3.795 which interpreted as **Very Satisfactory**. This suggests that there may be a number of advantageous effects when school administrators and master teachers have excellent interpersonal skills and are certified to mentor new educators. Training sessions can be delivered more successfully by school administrators and master teachers with strong interpersonal skills. For other teachers, their capacity for clear communication, attentive listening, and helpful criticism improves the learning environment. However, the indicators were assessed as **Unsatisfactory level** signifies a leadership approach that could harm the school culture. The school leader might be eroding teacher confidence, failing to create a collaborative or supportive workplace, and overlooking chances to mentor teachers effectively. This means that the school leader openly reproaches or rectifies fellow teachers in front of their colleagues, students, or other staff. Public correction may lead to feelings of humiliation or embarrassment, which can weaken the teacher's authority or morale. Panda and Mohany (2021) cited that school heads and master teachers who demonstrate strong interpersonal skills not only improve current practices but also help develop future leaders within the school. Their mentoring and training can prepare other teachers for leadership roles when school heads and master teachers excel in interpersonal competence and are equipped to train others, it leads to more effective professional development, enhanced teacher morale, better collaboration, smoother change management, improved student outcomes, and the cultivation of future leaders.

Table 4 presented the interpersonal competence of the school heads and master teachers in Lapu-Lapu City Division in terms of understanding and motivating.

Table 4. Interpersonal Competence of the Respondents in terms of Understanding and Motivating

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Understanding and Motivating			
1. He/ she tries hard enough to do almost any job in the school	4.04	0.77	Very Satisfactory
2. Treats all subordinates equally and fairly	4.57	0.57	Outstanding
3. Believes that people are born with certain aptitudes, capacities, and potentials	4.51	0.64	Outstanding
4. Does not believe that the only kind of recognition that means anything to a teacher is money	3.47	1.31	Very Satisfactory
5. Has an interest in doing work of which he/she can be proud of	4.26	0.70	Outstanding
6. Is lazy when not interested	2.20	1.11	Unsatisfactory
7. Tells what to do in a given situation especially when he/she knows the teacher well	4.13	0.74	Very Satisfactory
8. Believes that when a teacher has done a given piece of work, it is a sure sign that he/she is satisfied and properly placed	4.01	0.68	Very Satisfactory
9. Is faced with frustrating situations almost every day	2.12	1.13	Unsatisfactory
10. Fights frustration vigorously	3.80	0.95	Very Satisfactory
Factor mean	3.712		Very Satisfactory

As gleaned in the Table 4 on interpersonal competencies of the school heads and master teachers in terms of understanding and motivating. It was found out that the composite factor mean was 3.712 which interpreted as **Very Satisfactory**. This means that when school heads and master teachers demonstrate strong interpersonal competence in understanding and motivating their subordinates, and treat all individuals equally and fairly, several significant implications can be observed such as it builds trust and credibility within the school community. Teachers are more likely to feel secure and valued, knowing that their contributions are recognized fairly. Creates a positive work environment where teachers are more willing to go the extra mile and collaborate effectively.

This implies that the Interpersonal Competence of respondents in terms of Understanding and Motivating has significant implications for the overall effectiveness of leadership and team dynamics within the school environment.

When school principals or leaders find it difficult to comprehend and inspire their staff, it may result in disengagement, lowered morale, and poor communication. Leaders who lack awareness of their teachers' needs, strengths, and challenges might find it difficult to establish strong, trusting relationships, potentially obstructing collaboration and professional development. Furthermore, a lack of staff motivation may lead to reduced enthusiasm, diminished productivity, and increased turnover rates, which can ultimately affect student performance and the school's culture. For educational leaders, gaining a more profound insight into their team's requirements and offering suitable motivation is crucial for cultivating a constructive, supportive environment that promotes growth, creativity, and exceptional performance. Addressing shortcomings in this area of interpersonal competence can result in improved leadership, enhanced team unity, and superior results for both teachers and learners.

This was supported by Cahen & Davis, (2021) that when school heads and master teachers use their interpersonal competence to understand and motivate their subordinates while ensuring equal and fair treatment, it leads to a more trustworthy, motivated, and cohesive school environment. This fosters professional growth, enhances teacher retention, and positively impacts student outcomes.

Table 5 presented the interpersonal competence of the school heads and master teachers in Lapu-Lapu City Division in terms of positive attitudes.

Table 5. Interpersonal Competence of the Respondents in terms of Positive Attitude

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Positive Attitudes			
1. Studies facts carefully to study the attitudes of subordinates	4.263	0.661	Outstanding
2. Believes that the older the people are, the more fixed their attitudes	3.224	0.974	Satisfactory
3. Shows concern with employees/ teachers	4.526	0.599	Outstanding

4. Believes that teacher’s attitude has an effect on his / her teaching	4.263	0.719	Outstanding
5. Handle grievances and moral problems of the teachers	4.066	0.789	Very Satisfactory
6. Does not expect that teachers will leave their problems at home	3.197	0.817	Satisfactory
7. Does not recommend dismissal for a troublemaker	3.316	0.983	Satisfactory
8. Does not believe most teachers have bad feelings towards the school because they are underpaid	3.579	0.928	Very Satisfactory
9. Changes the bad attitudes of teachers	3.566	0.699	Very Satisfactory
10. Spends a lot of time with a new teacher to be sure the latter is well trained on his/her job	3.487	0.872	Very Satisfactory
Factor mean	3.749		Very Satisfactory

Table 5 on interpersonal competencies of the school heads and master teachers in terms of positive attitude. It was found out that the composite factor mean was 3.749 which interpreted as **Very Satisfactory**. This means that when school heads and master teachers demonstrate interpersonal competence through a positive attitude and genuine concern for their teachers, it can have profound implications for the school environment and its overall effectiveness. A positive attitude in school leadership and teaching roles involves maintaining an optimistic outlook, showing enthusiasm, and approaching challenges with a constructive mindset. It reflects resilience, encouragement, and an ability to motivate others. This implies that teachers who perceive that their leaders genuinely care about their well-being are more likely to feel valued and confident in their roles. This can lead to increased job satisfaction and a more positive attitude towards their work. An "outstanding" rating in interpersonal competence, especially in terms of positive attitude. This suggests that educators who believe their leaders truly care about their welfare are more inclined to feel appreciated and secure in their positions. This may result in greater job satisfaction and an improved outlook on their work means that a school head who is essential in influencing the overall educational experience. These leaders not only affect the immediate results within the school but also improve the wider social, emotional, and academic results for both teachers and students. Their leadership approach creates an atmosphere where people are inspired, involved, and appreciated, leading to the lasting success of the school community.

This was supported by the study of (Ross, 2019) that positive attitude from school heads and master teachers fosters a more pleasant and supportive work environment. This can lead to stronger interpersonal relationships and a more collaborative atmosphere. Teachers are more likely to support and encourage each other, creating a more cohesive and motivated team. Teachers are more likely to approach problems with a solutions-focused mindset when they feel supported and respected. Leaders who show genuine concern can mediate conflicts with empathy, helping to resolve issues more amicably and effectively. When school heads and master teachers exhibit a positive attitude and demonstrate genuine concern for their teachers, it results in improved teacher morale, a more supportive workplace environment, increased engagement, and strengthened professional relationships. This positive approach not only enhances the overall work experience for teachers but also positively influences student learning outcomes and fosters a more productive and harmonious school community.

Table 6 presents the interpersonal competence of the school heads and master teachers in Lapu-Lapu City Division in terms of problem-solving techniques.

Table 6. Interpersonal Competence of the Respondents in terms of Problem-Solving Techniques

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Problem-Solving Techniques			
1. Solves own problems by getting the detailed facts	4.079	0.707	Very Satisfactory
2. Believes that a group of people can usually find a better solution to a problem than one individual	4.079	0.707	Very Satisfactory
3. Knows the personalities of subordinates and makes use of his knowledge in solving a problem	4.118	0.816	Very Satisfactory
4. Does not believe that if people have problems bothering them, they should keep those to themselves and solve them the best way they can	3.382	1.107	Satisfactory
5. Makes and compares a list of solutions before deciding on one solution to a problem	4.184	0.668	Very Satisfactory
6. Consults with teachers in solving problems of the school	4.276	0.723	Outstanding
7. Faces problems accordingly once they are identified	4.250	0.751	Outstanding

8. Is good in interpersonal relation and encounters few problems in the area	4.026	0.765	Very Satisfactory
9. Has the courage to try possible solutions to a problem	4.355	0.667	Outstanding
10. Agrees that it is possible that there are teachers who are better in solving problems than a manager does	3.868	0.885	Very Satisfactory
Factor mean	4.062		Very Satisfactory

As surfaced on the Table 6, it was found out that the factor mean 4.062 defined **Very Satisfactory** that means the interpersonal competencies of school heads and mater teachers exhibit strong interpersonal competence in problem-solving, it means they effectively address and resolve issues while maintaining positive relationships with their colleagues. Effective problem-solving encourages teamwork by fostering open communication. School leaders and master teachers who handle difficulties skillfully create a team-oriented environment where colleagues feel appreciated and involved. Involving others in problem-solving assists in producing solutions that include different views, leading to more robust and broadly accepted results. However an "outstanding rating" for Interpersonal Competence concerning Problem-Solving Techniques indicates that the respondents excel in managing interpersonal challenges using effective and innovative problem-solving approaches.

This implies that interpersonal competence in problem-solving among school heads and master teachers involves addressing issues effectively while maintaining positive relationships. An exceptional score in interpersonal skills tied to problem-solving methods signifies a school leader who proficiently tackles challenges, regardless of their size, in a manner that aligns with the school's objectives and cultivates a positive, efficient atmosphere. The capacity to efficiently tackle problems has extensive consequences, ranging from better daily operations and increased teacher morale to improved student performance and reinforced connections with stakeholders. A leader possessing this skill set aids not just in the quick resolution of problems but also in the ongoing success and development of the school community.

This competency leads to a collaborative and efficient work environment, enhances teacher morale and engagement, builds trust in leadership, and supports professional development (Sumantri, 2019). Van Rooy, (2020) affirmed that teachers who perceive that their leaders genuinely care about their well-being are more likely to feel valued and confident in their roles. This can lead to increased job satisfaction and a more positive attitude towards their work.

Job Performance

Table 7 presents the job performance of the school heads and master teachers in terms of their instructional leadership.

Table 7. Job Performance of the Respondents in terms of Instructional Leadership

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Instructional Leadership			
1. Implemented and sustained priority improvement programs/projects (PIPs) that address the needs of the learners and help achieve the school and Division target performance within the school year.	4.368	0.690	Outstanding
2. Implemented programs/ projects/activities (PPAs) which promote 100% access to inclusive basic education within the school year.	4.303	0.633	Outstanding
3. Conducted M&E and Supervisory/TA activities to teachers which ensure quality delivery of Kto12 Curriculum Instruction and Assessment within the school year.	4.368	0.585	Outstanding
Factor mean	4.346		Outstanding

As shown in Table 7, the factor mean was 4.5346 which interpreted as **Outstanding** on the Job Performance of the Respondents in terms of Instructional Leadership which means that school heads and master teachers had implemented the priority improvement programs/ projects (PIPs) that address the needs of the learners and help achieve the school and Division target performance within the school year. School heads had conducted Monitoring and Evaluation and Supervisory activities to teachers which ensure quality delivery of Kto12 Curriculum.

This implies that instructional leadership role of school heads in guiding, supporting, and enhancing teaching and learning within their schools has significant implications for teachers and the overall school environment. An outstanding rating for instructional leadership indicates that the school leader is very effective in directing teaching

and learning activities within the school. The consequences of this reach well beyond merely the leadership alone. It enhances teacher effectiveness, student results, and overall school achievement. It fosters a culture of elevated standards, ongoing professional growth, and teamwork, all of which enhance educational experiences for students and lead to more rewarding, efficient roles for teachers. The beneficial effects of this type of leadership are experienced at every tier of the school, influencing classroom activities and overall policies, facilitating a nurturing and well-structured educational atmosphere where both teachers and students can prosper.

Villenes, M. R. (2019) supports that improving teaching quality and supporting teachers, instructional leaders contribute to better student outcomes, including higher achievement levels and improved engagement in the learning process.

Table 8 presents the job performance of the school heads and master teachers in terms of their learning environment.

Table 8. Job Performance of the Respondents in terms of Learning Environment

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Learning Environment			
1. Implemented and sustained programs which promote safe, conducive and friendly school learning environment for all learners and personnel.	4.526	0.553	Outstanding
2. Implemented ancillary programs and services which promote the holistic development of learners and personnel within the school year.	4.500	0.577	Outstanding
3. Implemented and sustained curricular and extra-curricular activities which promote holistic development of the learners.	4.474	0.621	Outstanding
Factor mean	4.500		Outstanding

As surfaced on the Table 8, it was found out that the factor mean 4.500 defined **Outstanding**, that means the job performance of school heads and mater teachers exhibit strong performance in learning environment. This means that they implemented and sustained programs which promote safe, conducive and friendly school learning environment for all learners and personnel. This implies that school heads and master teachers with high interpersonal skills can deliver more effective training sessions. n exceptional rating for fostering a positive learning environment indicates the school leader's capability to create and uphold a nurturing, inclusive, and efficient atmosphere for educators and learners alike. The consequences of this rating are extensive, affecting aspects such as teacher morale and retention, student performance, and the overall climate of the school.

School leaders who emphasize a constructive learning atmosphere promote a culture of teamwork, responsibility, and ongoing enhancement, thereby greatly boosting job performance across all tiers. This results in improved educational experiences for students, increased teacher satisfaction, and overall school achievement. Their ability to communicate clearly, listen actively, and provide constructive feedback enhances the learning experience for other teachers.

Wilson and Wineberg (2018) affirmed in their study that the job performance of school leaders and master teachers in promoting effective programs and ensuring a safe learning environment has significant implications. It leads to an enhanced learning environment, improved student achievement and engagement, increased teacher effectiveness, a stronger school community, and greater resilience and adaptability.

Table 9 presents the job performance of the school heads and master teachers in terms of human resource management and development.

Table 9. Job Performance of the Respondents in terms of Human Resource Management and Development

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Human Resource Management and Development			
1. Implemented and sustained Learning and Development (L&D) activities that enhance KSAs of teachers and non-teaching personnel within the school year.	4.355	0.626	Outstanding
2. Strengthened implementation of RPMS-IPCRF to teachers and non-teaching personnel within the prescribed RPMS cycle.	4.421	0.638	Outstanding
3. Updated teachers and personnel records as essential to performance management, promotion, and provision of personnel benefits.	4.368	0.670	Outstanding

Factor mean	4.381	Outstanding
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Table 9, presented the job performance of school heads and mater teachers in terms of human resource management and development that has a factor mean of 4.381 with verbal interpretation **Outstanding** which exhibits strong performance in aforementioned job performance. This means that part of the duties and responsibilities of school heads was to update teachers and personnel records with the strengthened implementation of RPMS-IPCRF to teachers and non-teaching personnel within the prescribed RPMS cycle. Thus, this implies that the job performance of school leaders and master teachers in human resource management and development is crucial for the effective implementation of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) and Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) for teacher. Successful human resource management demands an emphasis on positive reinforcement, ongoing professional growth, and fostering a culture where teachers sense their worth and receive support. Should these problems continue, it may result in decreased employee satisfaction, diminished motivation, and eventually, a detrimental effect on student success and organizational efficiency.

According to Woolfolk (2019) the school leaders and master teachers who perform well in human resource management can identify specific professional development needs based on RPMS/IPCRF evaluations. This targeted approach ensures that development programs are relevant and address actual areas of improvement. Thus, human resource management and development has significant implications for the implementation of RPMS/IPCRF for teachers. It leads to improved teacher performance and accountability, targeted professional development, enhanced motivation and engagement, strengthened leadership and school culture, and ultimately better school performance and student outcomes.

Table 10 presents the job performance of the school heads and master teachers in terms of school leadership and management operation.

Table 10. Job Performance of the Respondents in terms of School Leadership and Management Operation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
School Leadership and Management Operation			
1. Developed and implemented School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Implementation Plan (AIP)/ Annual Procurement Plan (APP) which establish priority goals and objectives for school priority improvement areas.	4.474	0.621	Outstanding
2. Directed, managed, utilized school funds based on priority needs contained in the approved SIP/AIP/APP/.	4.500	0.702	Outstanding
3. Established/strengthened partnerships and linkages with stakeholders by conducting activities e.g. advocacy, meetings and consultation, informing them of the development needs, goals and objectives of the school.	4.447	0.661	Outstanding
Factor mean	4.474		Outstanding

As shown in the Table 10 on the job performance of the school heads and master teachers in terms of school leadership and management operation and it was found out that the composite factor mean was 4.474 which interpreted as **Outstanding**. This means that school heads and master teachers had established the School Improvement Plan (SIP) and Annual Implementation Plan (AIP)/ Annual Procurement Plan (APP) which the priority goals and objectives for school improvement. This implies that the job performance of school leaders and master teachers plays a pivotal role in the effectiveness of school leadership and management operations, particularly in the context of implementing a School Improvement Plan (SIP).

A high rating for school leadership and management practices has significant effects on the job performance of all staff and the overall success of the institution. Successful school leaders who excel in management and guidance facilitate smooth operations, support staff, foster a positive school environment, and prioritize student success. Their capacity to make educated choices, promote teacher development, and encourage teamwork leads to enhanced teacher morale, job contentment, and retention. Furthermore, effective school leadership strengthens community ties, fosters student achievement, and establishes a strong basis for sustained success. In conclusion, exceptional leadership and management practices are essential for developing a flourishing educational setting where both faculty and students can excel. Obari, (2019) supports that leaders in school who perform well in managing school operations can effectively handle resistance to change. By addressing concerns and providing support, they facilitate smoother transitions during SIP and AIP implementation. Effective performance leads to well-planned and strategic initiatives, enhanced operational efficiency, improved school culture, increased engagement among teachers and students and developed and implemented best programs for school improvement.

Table 11 presents the job performance of the school heads and master teachers in terms of parents' involvement and community partnership.

Table 11. Job Performance of the Respondents in terms of Parents' Involvement and Community Partnership

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Parents' Involvement and Community Partnership			
1. Established school and family and community partnership for school performance.	4.553	0.598	Outstanding
2. Coordinated with stakeholders in the acquisition of learning materials, resources and equipment within target date	4.395	0.655	Outstanding
Factor mean	4.474		Outstanding

As resulted in Table 11 on the job performance of the school heads and master teachers in terms of parents' involvement and community partnership, the combined factor mean 4.474 was interpreted as **Outstanding**. This means that school leaders had established school and family and community partnership and had a constant coordination with stakeholders. The job performance of school leaders and master teachers significantly impacts the level of stakeholder and community involvement in school programs and activities.

This implies that the strong community involvement often translates into additional resources for school programs, including financial contributions, material donations, and volunteer services. When school leaders achieve an excellent rating for parental engagement and community collaboration, it significantly enhances job performance throughout the school. Educators gain from the enhanced support, resources, and teamwork that arise from robust connections among the school, parents, and the community. This leads to enhanced morale, lower stress levels, increased teacher involvement, and improved results for students. Additionally, the shared responsibility encouraged by these connections aids in cultivating a positive, flourishing school environment that benefits both teacher achievement and sustained school enhancement. In the end, strong school leadership regarding parental engagement and community collaborations fosters a more cooperative, resource-abundant, and successful educational setting for all parties involved.

This support enhances the implementation and sustainability of various initiatives. Egeberg & McConney (2019) agreed that when stakeholders and community members are actively involved, they provide holistic support to students, including mentorship, tutoring, and extracurricular opportunities. This comprehensive support contributes to improved student outcomes and overall well-being. By utilizing the community's combined knowledge and resources, it also promotes creative thinking and efficient problem-solving. In the end, effective leadership in this field guarantees that educational initiatives and programs are meaningful and well-supported, which benefits both students and the larger community.

Table 12 presents the job performance of the school heads and master teachers in terms of their plus factor.

Table 12. Job Performance of the Respondents in terms of Plus Factor

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Plus Factor			
1. Accomplished tasks and activities which fall beyond the actual duties and responsibilities	4.553	0.598	Outstanding

As resulted in Table 12, the factor mean of 4.553 was interpreted by Outstanding on their plus factor. This means that plus factor are additional qualities or contributions of teachers beyond their basic teaching responsibilities that positively impact the educational environment and student outcomes. It typically involves attributes or actions that enhance the effectiveness of their teaching and support the overall goals of the school. This implies that the job performance of school leaders and master teachers in terms of their plus factor has significant implications to enhanced school performance, improved teacher morale and professional development, stronger school-community relations, a positive school culture, and better student outcomes. Their extra efforts and leadership contribute to creating a dynamic and effective educational environment, benefiting all members of the school community. When school leaders receive outstanding ratings for the Plus Factor, they contribute extra qualities that inspire, motivate, and empower their staff, fostering a positive and productive school atmosphere. These characteristics extend past conventional leadership roles and promote an environment of innovation, teamwork, and ongoing enhancement. As supported by Grossman (2019) the effects on job performance are significant: educators exhibit greater motivation, involvement, and contentment in their positions, which results in enhanced teaching methods, increased student

success, and an encouraging school environment. In the end, effective leadership that exceeds fundamental practices creates a ripple effect, positively impacting staff, students, and the wider school community, and guaranteeing enduring success and sustainability.

Significant Relationships between Profile and Interpersonal Competencies

Table 13 present the significant relationship between the profile and personal competencies among the respondents.

Table 13. Significant Relationships between Profile and Interpersonal Competencies

Profile and Interpersonal Competence				
Pairwise	Value	P-value	Interpretation	Decision
Educational Attainment and Interpersonal competence				
role management	86.539	0.524	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
learning and training	66.589	0.919	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
understanding and motivating	63.276	0.915	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
positive attitudes	83.387	0.376	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
problem -solving techniques	76.355	0.467	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
Years of Experience and interpersonal competence				
role management	38.734	0.696	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
learning and training	43.444	0.41	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
understanding and motivating	51.22	0.11	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
positive attitudes	56.736	0.042	Significant	Failed to accept the Ho
problem -solving techniques	26.365	0.923	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
Seminars and trainings and interpersonal competence				
role management	272.416	0.087	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
learning and training	208.412	0.855	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
understanding and motivating	178.729	0.981	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
positive attitudes	294.938	< .001	Significant	Failed to accept the Ho
problem -solving techniques	251.699	0.023	Significant	Failed to accept the Ho
S- significant; NS - Not significant				

Table 13 indicates significant relationship between the profile and interpersonal competencies of the school heads and master teachers. It was found out that in the pairwise values of the profile of the respondents in terms of their educational attainment and interpersonal competencies, the p- values are greater than alpha value of 0.05, that leads to accepting the null hypothesis. This means that there were no significant relationship. However on the years of experience and interpersonal competencies, the computed p-values on the variables were higher that alpha values, which implies that there were no significant relationship, except on the relationship between the years of experience and positive attitudes since the p-value is 0.042. This is also confirmed by the p-values found in Table 13 wherein all figures are greater than the level of significance (0.05) except of the significant relationship of the seminars and training in interpersonal competencies in terms of positive attitudes and problems solving techniques ($p = 0.001$ and $0.023 < \alpha = 0.05$). This means that there is a significant relationship between the seminar/training attended by the school heads and master teachers to their positive attitudes and problem-solving techniques.

These findings imply that the enumerated profile variables cannot be all considered as predictors of school heads and master teachers and their interpersonal competencies. However, this leads to the reason of rejecting the null hypothesis, thus there is a significant on seminars/training and interpersonal competencies in terms of positive attitude and problem-solving techniques. This implies that interpersonal competencies do not show direct significant effect on the school heads and master teachers' performance. However, the ultimately determine the performance of the school heads and master teachers based on their compassion and dedications to do the profession.

When a significant relationship exists between profile characteristics and interpersonal competencies, it underscores the importance of tailoring leadership development efforts to improve these competencies in school heads and other educational leaders. The relationship suggests that factors such as experience, leadership style, and personal background can influence a leader’s ability to interact effectively with others. Schools should invest in professional development opportunities that foster these competencies, as they can significantly impact teacher satisfaction, collaboration, conflict management, community engagement, and overall school success. Ultimately, enhancing interpersonal competencies in leadership will contribute to a more positive and productive school environment, benefiting staff, students, and the wider school community. Furthermore, the no significance between profile traits (like experience, age, or education) and different interpersonal skills indicates that personal history or demographics might have minimal impact on the cultivation or success of these abilities. The implications highlight the significance of training initiatives, leadership growth, and workplace culture in nurturing essential interpersonal skills, rather than concentrating on individual characteristics.

This was supported by Sumantri (2019) the profile of school heads and master teachers does not significantly influences their interpersonal competencies. However competent school heads show their competencies affect their ability to communicate effectively, build relationships, resolve conflicts, and lead teams. Understanding this relationship helps in recognizing the attributes that contribute to effective school leadership .

Table 14 present the significant relationship between the profile and job performance among the respondents.

Table 14. Significant Relationships between Profile and Job Performance

Profile and Job satisfaction				
Educational Attainment and Job Performance	Value	p	Interpretation	Decision
instructional leadership	19.024	0.751	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
learning environment	24.27	0.446	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
human resource management and development	19.68	0.478	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
school leadership and management operation	31.474	0.141	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
parents’ involvement and community partnership	24.196	0.234	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
plus factor	8.419	0.394	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
Years of Experience and Job Performance	Value	p	Not Significant	
instructional leadership	10.723	0.553	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
learning environment	7.793	0.801	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
human resource management and development	14.354	0.157	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
school leadership and management operation	13.764	0.316	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
parents’ involvement and community partnership	5.576	0.85	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
plus factor	6.683	0.154	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho
Seminars and trainings and Job Performance	Value	p		
instructional leadership	113.19	< .001	Significant	Failed to accept the Ho
learning environment	147.83	< .001	Significant	Failed to accept the Ho
human resource management and development	86.027	0.005	Significant	Failed to accept the Ho
school leadership and management operation	110.76	< .001	Significant	Failed to accept the Ho

parents' involvement and community partnership	90.711	0.002	Significant	Failed to accept the Ho
plus factor	26.528	0.23	Not Significant	Failed to reject the Ho

The Table 14 exposes that there is no significant relationship between the profile variables in terms of educational attainment, years of experience and the job performance ($p = > \alpha = 0.05$). This is also validated by the p-values found in Table 14 wherein all figures in educational attainment and years of experience to job performance are greater than the level of significance (0.05). These findings signify that the enumerated profile variables cannot be considered as determinants of job performance. It was noticed that the computed p-values of the variables are higher than the level of significance which leads to the decision accept the null hypothesis, it is therefore, there no significant relationships exist between them.

However, on the relationship between the profile in terms of seminars/ training and the job performance, it was revealed that only plus factor show not significant while the instructional leadership, learning environment, human resource management and development, school leadership and management operation and parents' involvement and community partnership found a significant relationship since the computed p-values were lower that the alpha value 0.05, thus this reject the null hypothesis , therefore there is significant relationship.

This implies that demographic profile is not considered predictor on job performance. Regardless of the educational attainment and years of leadership experiences of the school heads and master teachers and and job performance on their OPCRf, attaining training and seminars have significant implications for their job performance. These professional development opportunities enhance their leadership skills, instructional practices, and interpersonal competencies. They also contribute to improved organizational efficiency and support (Furtak et al., 2019).

According to Wordu (2018) training and seminars attended by school heads and master teachers have profound implications for their job performance. These professional development opportunities can significantly impact various aspects of their roles, including leadership effectiveness, instructional quality, and overall school improvement. Training in leadership and management equips school heads with advanced decision-making skills. This leads to more strategic and effective decisions regarding school operations and initiatives.

Table 15 present the significant relationship between the interpersonal competencies and job performance among the respondents.

Table 15. Significant Relationships between Interpersonal Competencies and Job Performance

Indicators	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
role management and				
instructional leadership	.424**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
learning environment	.526**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
human resource management and development	.494**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
school leadership and management operation	.417**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
parents' involvement and community partnership	.591**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
plus factor	.481**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
learning and training and ...				Failed to accept the Ho
instructional leadership	.395**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
learning environment	.355**	0.002	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
human resource management and development	.448**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
school leadership and management operation	.319**	0.005	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
parents' involvement and community partnership	.489**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho

plus factor	.522**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
understanding and motivating and ...				Failed to accept the Ho
instructional leadership	.261*	0.023	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
learning environment	.362**	0.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
human resource management and development	.344**	0.002	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
school leadership and management operation	0.213	0.065	not significant	Failed to reject Ho
parents' involvement and community partnership	.449**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
plus factor	.452**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
positive attitudes; and ...				Failed to accept the Ho
instructional leadership	.477**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
learning environment	.421**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
human resource management and development	.556**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
school leadership and management operation	.408**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
parents' involvement and community partnership	.488**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
plus factor	.321**	0.005	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
problem -solving techniques				Failed to accept the Ho
instructional leadership	.452**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
learning environment	.580**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
human resource management and development	.594**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
school leadership and management operation	.559**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
parents' involvement and community partnership	.627**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
plus factor	.461**	<.001	significant	Failed to accept the Ho
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

Table 15 shows that the school heads and mater teachers' interpersonal competencies has significant relationship to their job performance ($p < \alpha = 0.05$), except on the relationship between understanding and school leadership and management operation with a computed p- value of 0.065 which leads to a decision accept the null hypothesis, therefore not significant. This implies that there is enough evidence to support the hypotheses. In other words, the study's findings provides convincing evidence that the variables being studied are related of have significant effect on each other. Nonetheless, it is important to note that non-significant results should not be equated with being insignificant or meaningless. The important connections between interpersonal competencies and job performance in different areas (excluding school leadership and management operations) indicate that interpersonal skills are vital in enhancing collaboration, teaching efficacy, and employee morale. Nevertheless, for the leadership and management of schools, additional technical, organizational, and strategic skills might be necessary.

The notable connections between interpersonal skills and job performance indicate that robust interpersonal abilities, including effective communication, teamwork, empathy, and problem resolution, are essential for improving overall

job performance in different roles within the school setting. According to Egeberg and McConney (2019) these provide valuable information that can contribute to the collective knowledge and guide for future research. School leaders, educators, and personnel exhibiting strong interpersonal skills are more inclined to nurture constructive workplace relationships, establish a collaborative and supportive environment, and handle conflicts efficiently, all of which enhance productivity, morale, and job satisfaction. These skills are crucial in fostering a positive school environment, where collaboration and respect for one another are emphasized, resulting in improved performance in teaching and administrative positions. Therefore, focusing on enhancing interpersonal skills can greatly influence and boost job performance in educational environments.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the relationship between interpersonal competencies and job performance of school heads in Lapu-Lapu City Division is both significant and multifaceted. Interpersonal competencies such as role management, learning and training, understanding and motivating, positive attitudes, and problem-solving techniques are critical in shaping how effectively school heads perform their roles. School heads with strong interpersonal competencies are better equipped to lead their schools effectively. Their ability to communicate clearly, empathize that job performance of the school heads based on OPCRF. The relationship between interpersonal competencies and job performance of school heads in Lapu-Lapu City Division underscores the importance of these skills in educational leadership. Effective interpersonal competencies enable school heads to lead more efficiently, foster a positive work environment, engage with the community, and support student success. Enhancing these competencies through professional development and training can lead to improved job performance and more successful school management. The study highlights the critical interconnections between interpersonal competencies, role management, learning and training, motivation, positive attitudes, and problem-solving techniques in enhancing job performance across various domains such as instructional leadership, learning environments, human resource management and development, school leadership and operations, as well as parental involvement and community partnerships. Shows that interpersonal skills are crucial for improving the job performance of school leaders.

Strong interpersonal abilities, such as effective communication, empathy, teamwork, and conflict management, are crucial for establishing positive connections with teachers, students, parents, and the wider community. These skills allow school leaders to create a nurturing and inspiring school environment, tackle challenges in advance, and guide their institutions in reaching academic and operational objectives. Skillful management of relationships enhances leadership results and also benefits the overall learning atmosphere, fostering the enduring success and growth of students and teachers alike. Therefore, enhancing interpersonal skills among school leaders is essential for boosting leadership effectiveness and school outcome.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. School Heads and Master Teachers shall strengthen their interpersonal competencies to achieve the educational leadership goal through seminar and training school leadership and management operation.
2. Training needs assessment shall be conducted to appropriately address School Heads and Master teachers' gaps and concerns in their leadership role and job performance.
3. Distinguished and highly proficient School Heads and Master Teachers shall give support to teachers through mentoring and coaching.
4. A functional reward system should be established to recognize performing school heads and master teachers that are performing.
5. Utilization of the proposed enhancement program.

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